

THE IMPORTANCE OF TEACHING STREET SAFETY TO CHILDREN IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *Safety is the most important factor at present. Safety skills are important at any age, and for preschoolers, developing it will help prevent many problems in the future. The main part of this article is devoted to the importance and significance of the formation of a child's safe behavior on the street.*

Keywords: *safety, behavior, traffic rules, street, skills, environment.*

ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ДЕТЕЙ УЛИЧНОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ В ДОШКОЛЬНЫХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ УЧРЕЖДЕНИЯХ

Аннотация. *Важным фактором на данный момент является безопасность. Безопасность важна в любом возрасте, и для дошкольников ее развитие поможет предотвратить многие проблемы в будущем. Основная часть данной статьи посвящена важности и значимости формирования безопасного поведения ребенка на улице.*

Ключевые слова: *безопасность, поведение, правила дорожного движения, улица, навыки, окружающая среда.*

Teachers should know definition of personal security and reliable educational environment in the work of an educational institution. So that, it is necessary note the concept of personal security, which is determined by three interrelated factors: environmental moment, human factor and safety factor.

The environment is everything, that affects a person, who is financial and demographic factors, his family, etc. *human factor* is his reaction to a threat. *Safety factor* is the mental and physiological ways that a person uses to shield themselves from unsafe and hectic environments.

The most important part is safety on the road and learning rules and how to teach safe behavior to preschoolers.

The most valuable thing is the health and life of the child. Therefore, in kindergarten, great attention must be paid to the issue of the safety of children on the streets and roads of the city. Teaching the road and traffic rules takes a special place in the preschoolers life.

Fostering safe behavior in children is one of the most important objectives of a preschool institution. A child becomes a pedestrian much earlier than he becomes prepared for being pedestrian by his knowledge, efforts, development. From the first days of a child's stay in kindergarten, his upbringing and education should be organized in such a way that by the time he moves from kindergarten to school he can easily navigate his immediate surroundings, be able to observe and correctly evaluate traffic situations, and have the skills of safe behavior in these situations. It is at kindergarten where all children can and should receive systematized information about safe behavior on the street and roads and acquire the necessary skills to follow them.

Certainly, children should know safety behavior first, because children always depends on the street; coming to preschool educational institutions, playing with friends, walking with

parents. Most people might think parents or teachers are responsible for children all the time. But we should understand one thing, when preschoolers understand rules by themselves. Of course, reminding and teaching safety behavior and safety in the street is responsibility of teachers and parents.

Teachers should make colorful methods and interactive forms for familiarizing children to safety in the street. For instance, playing games, reading books about traffic rules or fairytales about safety, cognitive activities, communicative activities, productive activities and etc.

Likewise, playing games is the most important and effective method to teaching preschoolers. Because children should not think activity like a lesson and collaboration learning and playing will be more effective to preschoolers because they will remember it easily. In addition, picture cards are effective too and also teachers can use it to compose a story. Of course, there is the section Transport and safety in “Ilk qadam” PEI curriculum. Children learn vehicles; traffic rules; emergency vehicles; however, the section does not have enough safety behavior in the street. In my view, children should understand what they should do if they have an accident in the street. For example, if the ball bounces off the road, children should understand that they should not try to take the ball. In addition, pedestrian safety is important to children too. Preschoolers should know how to cross the road, how they should behave on the road or in public transport. Teachers should use various methods to teach these factors. For instance, using cards (good-bad) are useful method because children can remember easily what they should do and what they should not do.

Не высовывайся в окна транспорта!

Не садись в автобус с мороженым!

(1-picture: bad habit vs good habit)

As well as, teachers should do trainings about safety of the road.

Here is an example of road safety training:

The goal of preventive work is to teach children about road safety rules as a pedestrian and passenger in a vehicle. **Objectives by age: 3-4 years:** to form primary ideas about the main

sources of dangers on the roads and streets (transport) and ways of safe behavior, using various types of children's activities (productive, motor, musical and artistic, labor); **4-5 years:** expand information and familiarize with methods of safe behavior in some standard dangerous situations (on the carriageway) and teach to follow them while being reminded by an adult; **5-6 years:** expand and clarify knowledge about safe behavior on the road and streets; ensure the development of methods of safe behavior in some standard dangerous situations (on the carriageway) and use them without being reminded by an adult; **6-7 years:** expand, clarify and systematize knowledge about dangerous situations on the road and streets; to expand and form behavioral skills in standard and non-standard dangerous situations on the road; to achieve conscious implementation of the basic rules of safe behavior on the road and in transport.

Work to educate children about safe behavior on the road should be systematic, continually, and methodical. It should not be an independent section, but a logical element of all activities. It should consist of outside playing games, productive activities and etc.

There are so many forms of working to teach children traffic and road rules;

-2-3 times a week make conversations about safe behavior, traffic accidents, attitude to traffic rules and accidents and etc.

- didactic games, puzzles and cartoons about “The road safety”

- teaching poems, reading and make story,

- develop mathematical concepts, teach space orientation and directions (left, right side).

- making puppet shows or theatre about “Safety on the road”.

The main thing is collaboration with parents and police inspectors. Preschoolers should understand the main rules from police inspectors and parents will help to remind rules to children. Teacher can invite police inspectors and children will see and feel how inspectors work and traffic rules effectively. Teachers can invite parents in PEI and make interactive activities for example: “Preschoolers and parents” day; questionnaire of the parents; release the newspaper; quizzes; “Family-master class” and etc.

Working with parents is the most effective way, because children are always excited to see parents and work together, it gives positive result in the acquisition of knowledge by children on the road and traffic rules. In addition, they bring all participants in the educational process together.

In conclusion, road safety is always important in the contemporary world. Vehicles are increasing continually and we can not stop it. For that reason, we should start to know safety behavior on the street from preschool age.

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